

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/376314475>

World Journal of Management and Economics INHERENT CHALLENGES IN TRAINING EFFECTIVENESS

Article · December 2023

CITATIONS

0

READS

51

4 authors, including:

[Laxman Kumar Tripathy](#)

SaiBalaji International Institute of Management sciences

51 PUBLICATIONS 7 CITATIONS

SEE PROFILE

INHERENT CHALLENGES IN TRAINING EFFECTIVENESS

Kuldip Charak,

Director, Faculty of Management, Navsahyadri Group of Institutes, Pune

Rupesh Patil,

Principal, Faculty of Engineering, Navsahyadri Group of Institutes, Pune

Laxman Tripathy,

Director, Saibalji International Institute of Management Sciences, Pune

Kavita Joshi,

Assistant Prof. Faculty of Management, Navsahyadri Group of Institutes, Pune

Abstract:

Training effectiveness is not solely dependent on the rigorous adherence of the steps involved in various training models. But its role is to cover much larger expanse of the canvas. Educating and training though remains the core objective of its efforts yet the other and the more important dimension is to make the participants unlearn the obsolete and willingly and objectively acquire the latest skills/ knowledge required for maintaining the utmost desired productivity. Probably the principles of memory functioning would be needed to be invoked here. Besides the trainees are matured adults who can apply their experience to decide the wrong and right at their own without warranting external intervention. Most of the times they prefer not welcoming any such interventions in their matters – personal or professional unless feel thoroughly convinced. In such scenario different tools of learning need to be institutionalized – andragogy, heutagogy etc. Effective transfer of learning would always be the key objective of ensuring training effectiveness but this entire exercise is not bereft of inherent challenges – certain surmountable and certain insurmountable. So the biggest challenge would be how to minimize the scale of insurmountable challenges of the game to ensure efficacy of training interventions pushed in at various levels and stages.

Key words: training effectiveness, identification of training needs/ analysis, un-train & re-train, transfer of learning etc.

1. Introduction and Literature:

“Training is, more often than not, always targeting a visible and tangible change in the degree of knowledge, skills and attitudes. The first two, of course, are more and easily measurable than the third. The increasingly turbulent environment – high-tech, globalization, instant, mobile, extremely diverse”¹ – has further necessitated the need for proper and systematic acquisition of its elements. Therefore, “by learning human beings can gain any experience – knowledge, capabilities

and skills. It includes the unconscious process of comprehension and fixation – involuntary memorizing, of the material”². It includes “...any change in the general activity of an organism the effects of which persist and recur over a period of time and which are strengthened by repetition and practice”³. Besides, “it refers to a planned process that directs learning towards achieving specific outcomes, leading to achieving performance objectives”⁴. Additionally training is “A planned process to modify attitude, knowledge and skill behaviour through learning experience to achieve effective performance in an activity or range of activities. Its purpose in the work situation is to develop the abilities of the individual and to satisfy current and future manpower needs of the organization”⁵. In the similar vein Robert H Rouda & Mitchell E Kusy Jr., describe “Training is a learning process directly tied to specific situational results. The focus is usually based on improving individual and group behaviour and performance, and on results to the organization”⁶. Another description given by Dr. Carter McNamara, “...is often interpreted as the activity when an expert and learner work together to effectively transfer information from the expert to the learner (to enhance a learner’s knowledge, skills or attitudes) so the learner can better perform a current task or job”⁷. So “precisely the training is more focused learning directed towards achievement of certain goals or to, simply put, bridge the gap between the expected level of performance and the actual level of performance. The effectiveness of training can be measured by examining what a person could do before the training and what he or she could do after it”⁸. Also “Training is the acquisition of technology, which permits employees to perform their present job to standards. It improves human performance on the job the employee is presently doing or is being hired to do. Further, it is given when new technology is introduced into the workplace”⁹. On the other hand “...the investment that a company makes in training shows employees that they are valued. When employees feel appreciated and challenged through learning opportunities they may feel more satisfaction and engagement toward their job. Training programs allow strengthen the skills and knowledge that each employee needs to improve in order to contribute to the organization’s intellectual capital. Intellectual capital comprises the knowledge, skills and abilities that employees carry around in their heads”¹⁰.

Role of Memory:

Memory is one of the vital cogs in the entire scheme of ensuring effectiveness in training & development efforts. Though no one is sure, but most research suggests that there are at least three basic types – named for the kind of information it handles: episodic, semantic and procedural¹¹.

- Episodic memory – any memory of a specific event that happened while you were present is an episodic memory, such as what you had for dinner yesterday or where you were last Friday night;
- Semantic memory – contains generalized knowledge of the world that does not involve memory of a specific event. For example, you can answer a question like “Are wrenches pets or tools?” without remembering any specific episode in which you learned that wrenches are tools.

- Procedural memory, also called as skill memory, involves how to do things – how to ride a bicycle, read a map, swim etc. Often, a procedural memory consists of a complicated sequence of movements that cannot be described adequately in words.

Memory Processes¹²

Remembering something requires three basic processes as depicted in the following diagram.

1. The item must be encoded – put in a form that can be placed in memory.
2. It must be stored or maintained in the memory.
3. It must be retrieved or recovered from memory.

If any of these processes fails to operate properly, forgetting will occur. In fact human memory system allows us to encode, store and retrieve a lifetime of experiences. Without it, we would have no sense of who we are.

Three Stages of Memory

Any memory, whatever its content, is the result of encoding, storage and retrieval. Why then do people remember some information far better and far longer than other information? Why do some stimuli leave more than a fleeting impression and others remain in memory forever? There are number of reasons, but the most important involves how extensively information is processed. The most influential theories of memory suggest that in order for information to become firmly embedded in memory, it must pass through three stages of processing: sensory memory, short-term memory, and long-term memory¹³.

1. Sensory memory – in the first stage where the information is received through senses – sight, sounds, for example – is held in sensory registers for a fraction of seconds.
2. Short-term memory – Information in sensory registers may be attended to, analyzed and encoded as a meaningful pattern processed by the perception will get recorded in this stage of the memory otherwise the information will disappear in 20 seconds or so.
3. Long-term memory – if the information in short-term memory is further processed, it may be encoded in the long-term memory, where it may remain indefinitely.

Here is a very basic overview of the human memory system. The first stage captures information that the eyes, ears and other sensory organs pick up from the environment. In the second stage distinct patterns of the energy, such as recognizable

images or understandable words, are briefly held in consciousness. The third stage allows information to be retained for use hours, days, or even years later. Following diagram elucidates three-stage human memory system.

Rehearsal and Levels of Processing Memory¹⁴

There are two basic types of memory rehearsal:

- Maintenance Rehearsal – involves repeating an item over and over, as you might do to use a new telephone number. This method can keep an item active in the short-term memory but it is ineffective for encoding information into long-term memory till finally it happens.
- Elaborate Rehearsal is far more effective, which involves thinking about how new material relates to information already stored in long-term memory. For example, just repeating a new person’s name to you is not a very effective strategy for memorizing it. Instead try relating the situation, place, and occasion or at the event that person met you will help remember his name. The simplest reason here is you have used the relationships in the memory – networking.

We have seen that information that is attended to and perceived is encoded into short-term memory. If it is not rehearsed or if it is displaced by new information, this piece of information is lost. Chunking, using information already in long-term memory can help hold more information in short-term memory. The diagram below is self-explanatory.

The focus of training and development is to register the maximum amount of information in the long-term memory of the participants. During the period of training there has to be effective ways and means to encourage proper memory rehearsal of knowledge, skills and attitudinal activities to ensure desired transfer of learning.

Learn, Unlearn and Relearn:

The biggest challenge with the trainers is how to make their trainees unlearn the obsolete and redundant knowledge and skills and make them learn the most advanced and latest skill set. Organizations have to create those avenues and opportunities for their workforce to keep them highly motivated and productive. “.....similar transformative opportunity exists from the study of schools that radically rethink aspects of education; close examination of these non-traditional schools, such as The Big Picture [BP] schools that can help us see our practice as educators in a different light and can challenge our notions of teacher learning”¹⁵. But “unlike machines or computers, people do not have a “delete” or “off” button, unless in cases of brain pathology or death, respectively. Traces of old behavior, practices and routines remain stored in human being’s long-term memory, ready for re-use when activated by internal or external stimuli (Fiske and Taylor, 1991)”¹⁶. Part of the learning/ unlearning efforts, there is also something called as

forgetting that also plays a vital role in cognitive operations of a human being. Wherein “Forgetting is useful as it enables the reduction of the influence of old knowledge on cognitive and behavioral processes (Grisold et al., 2017)”¹⁷.

On the other hand, there are organizations those are called as learning organizations to ensure continuous learning/ upgrading/ upskilling activities are conducted regularly and in a routine fashion. Thus “Learning organizations are usually perceived as organizations that excel in individual and organizational learning, which renders them resilient to challenges both internally and externally. They are considered organizations that thrive on the synergy of individual and collective learning, which increases their transformation ability with the goal of sustained viability”¹⁸. To mitigate the challenges, organizations also “..... put emphasis on exploring the linkages between unlearning and relearning in organizations. When speaking of learning-forgetting-unlearningrelearningdynamics, it is a challenge to determine if these processes happen sequentially orsimultaneously”¹⁹.For example, Turc and Baumard (2007) believe that “unlearning and relearning occur sequentially in the way that unlearning triggers the process of relearning”²⁰. And “when it comes to the desired outcome – new knowledge, Cegarra-Navarro et al. (2011) consider unlearning required for forgetting old knowledge followed by relearning and developing new knowledge”²¹. In addition, Cegarra-Navarro et al. (2014) “consider the “unlearning context” in which forgetting-unlearning-relearning dynamics occurs”²². In that way, “unlearning is often considered a prerequisite for effective relearning (Zhao et al., 2013), which occurs through the process of forgetting or discarding the knowledge that has become obsolete or irrelevant in the newly emerged circumstance”²³. Therefore, “unlearning is always a point of departure from the known into the partially or completelyunknown, which is a cause of insecurity. However, if the leap into the unknown is made in a learning organization, organizational members could count on mutual support and ongoing dialogue as a process in which interpretation occurs collectively, followed by a joint exploration of newly needed knowledge”²⁴.

In addition, “whenever necessary, organizational members of a learning organization are open to inaction (Vince, 2008) when matters are individually and collectively reflected upon, new questions are asked and not immediately answered, new perspectives are brought to surface and new patterns of thinking emerge”²⁵. “The reason could be found in the importance of work-life balance in innovation for which outdated or unnecessary knowledge can become an obstacle. Organizational forgetting was also found to be a critical determinant of innovation performance as found by Huang et al. (2018)”²⁶. “It is also logical that the study by Wong et al. (2018) found that unlearning is positively related with organizational readiness, which is a prerequisite for further development and innovation. However, it is important to advance studies regarding factors that could facilitate unlearning and relearning”²⁷. For instance, Usman et al. (2018) found that “ethical leadership characterized by honesty and accountability facilitate unlearning of destructive and inappropriate behaviors and practices in individuals. It is expected that transformative leadership would be found to be a strong facilitator of the unlearning process followed by relearning. It is also expected that unlearning would be found crucial for double-loop organizational learning. Further studies of these interactions would require different methodological approaches”²⁸.But we also need to remember that “Past learning inhibits new learning: Before organizations will try new ideas, they must unlearn old ones by discovering their inadequacies and then discarding them . . . Top managers can stimulate their own unlearning and new learning in at least three ways: They

can listen to dissents, convert events into learning opportunities and adopt experimental frames of reference”²⁹. So “instead of conceptualizing the unlearning process as discarding, it seems more relevant to see it as a process of reflecting on the troubled business model and reducing the firm’s reliance on it”³⁰.

Challenges in Training:

“A range of challenges are faced by organisations and HRD professionals in managing and implementing effective HR T&D, particularly in the climate of globalisation, and the new technological revolution begins with the importance of human capital in HRD practice, their education and technical training, and also their communication and language skills. Human resources’ learning and motivation are also described as important features of effective HRD practices”³¹. “The central factor in HRD is the human resources or the human capital in an organization. They are viewed as the driving force for the success of organizations because of their skills, competencies, knowledge and experience (Becker, 1975; Schmidt & Lines, 2002; Harrison & Kessels, 2004)”³²⁻³⁴. Moreover, “it has been suggested that for organizations to compete successfully in a global economy, it is important to hire sufficiently educated and skilled employees and provide them with lifelong learning (Nadler & Wiggs, 1986; Chalofsky & Reinhart, 1988; Nadler & Nadler, 1989; O’Connell, 1999; Streumer et al, 1999; Low, 1998; Harrison, 2000; Sadler-Smith et al, 2000)”³⁵⁻⁴¹. However, “these are some of the problems faced by employers and organisations and seen as a hindrance to the effective management, training and development of human resources in a global economy (Roberts & McDonald, 1995)”⁴². In specific context, “the literature has indicated that there is a shortage of HRD professionals who are skilled and experienced systems thinkers (Bing et al, 2003), and who have the ability to manage the vast and specialized function of HRD across organizations (Eidgahy, 1995)”⁴³⁻⁴⁴.

“Successfully measuring effectiveness in management training and development can be a difficult task. Design of a valid measurement programme should include evaluation in key areas; including emotional reaction and knowledge gain measured after training interventions. Behavioral change and organizational impact measurements should be used on a longer time horizon to evaluate the progress and currency of the management development programme”⁴⁵.

2 Research Methodology:

Conduct of training for various purposes and objectives is the run of the mill due to rapidly changing technologies and human requirements. Organizations use various tools to ensure and measure the effectiveness of the training so imparted. In spite of all out efforts the corporates encounter with huge challenges in its delivery and final outcome of such interventions – to achieve desired transfer of learning at the end every training program. This necessitated to delve deeper into this issue and bring out possible outcomes through this study.

Research Data: Primary data has been used for this research that has been sourced from different industry - both manufacturing and service industry located in and around Pune city of State of Maharashtra. All put together valid/ cleaned data from 106 respondents has been used. This was collected with the help of a questionnaire that was sent across all the respondents through digital means.

**Volume 15 | Special Issue 03 | MARKETING MANAGEMENT-
TOPICAL ISSUES & CHALLENGES**

Sampling: A simple random sampling technique was used in the selection of the industry from the huge databank of industry collected from Registrar of Companies (ROC) Pune. To ensure maximum reach to the industry, no more than 2 samples were collected from a particular Co. In this process, the companies having their annual turnover of more than 15 Cr were only selected. Samples were collected from the HR/ Tech.Managers to get real pulse of the challenges faced by them.

To systematically carry out this research, following objectives were listed:

Objectives:

1. To identify the reasons for improper Identification of Training Needs and Training Need Analysis.
2. To list the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees.
3. To find out the challenges faced in quantifying the ‘transfer of learning’ to ensure training effectiveness.

All the above Objectives were supported by formulating of required hypothesis as listed below. These hypothesis were further bifurcated in factors that helped us designing the questionnaire.

Hypothesis:

1. H0: Identification of Training Needs and Training Needs Analysis is not important to ensure Training Effectiveness.
H1: It is significantly important to follow the process of Identification of Training Needs and carry out Training Needs Analysis.
2. H0: Listing out the difficulties faced in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is not necessary.
H1: Listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary.
3. H0: Quantifying the ‘transfer of learning’ is not important to ensure training effectiveness.
H1: It is significantly important to find out the challenges faced during quantification of ‘Transfer of Learning’ to ensure training effectiveness.

Table-1. Mapping the Objectives, Hypothesis and Factors.

Sr.	Objectives	Hypothesis (H0)	Hypothesis (H1)	Factors
1	To identify the reasons for improper Identification of Training Needs and Training Need Analysis.	Identification of Training Needs and Training Needs Analysis is not important to ensure Training Effectiveness.	It is significantly important to follow the process of Identification of Training Needs and carry out Training Needs Analysis.	-Identification of Training Needs -Training Needs analysis
2	To list the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees.	Listing out the difficulties faced in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is not necessary.	Listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary	-Un-training -Re-training
3	To find out the challenges faced in quantifying the 'transfer of learning' to ensure training effectiveness	Quantifying the 'transfer of learning' is not important to ensure training effectiveness	It is significantly important to find out the challenges faced during quantification of 'Transfer of Learning' to ensure training effectiveness	-Evaluation& analysis of Summative feedback -Transfer of Learning
4	Other Factors used during the course of Research		-Design of Training -Implementation of Training -Quantification of Training	

Table 2 Reliability and Normality Tests of the Data

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	106	100.0
	Excluded ^a	0	.0
	Total	106	100.0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Table 3

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.792	10

Table 4

Normality Statistics		
Averages		
N	Valid	106
	Missing	0
Skewness		.475
Std. Error of Skewness		.235
Kurtosis		-.159
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.465

3 Data Analysis:

Hypothesis – 1.

- H0: Identification of Training Needs and Training Needs Analysis is not important to ensure Training Effectiveness.
- H1: It is significantly important to follow the process of Identification of Training Needs and carry out Training Needs Analysis.

Table 5

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Proper Identification of Training Needs of employees is a huge task and it is never complete in all respects	106	4.68	.469	4	5
Scientific Training Needs Analysis is next to impossible	106	4.75	.432	4	5

Table 6

Friedman Test**Ranks**

	Mean Rank
Proper Identification of Training Needs of employees is a huge task and it is never complete in all respects	1.46
Scientific Training Needs Analysis is next to impossible	1.54

Table 7

Test Statistics^a

N	106
Chi-Square	1.231
df	1
Asymp. Sig.	.027

a. Friedman Test

Identification of Training Needs and Training Needs Analysis is important to ensure Training Effectiveness, $\chi^2 = 1.23, p > .05$.

Hypothesis – 2.

- H0: Listing out the difficulties faced in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is not necessary.
- H1: Listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary.

Table 8

KMO and Bartlett's Test		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.500
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	20.462
	df	1
	Sig.	.000
Communalities		
	Initial	Extraction
Completely Un-train any trainee is not possible	1.000	.712
Fully Re-train the trainees as desired is another challenge	1.000	.712
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

Table 9

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Tota l	% of Vari ance	Cumul ative %	Tot al	% of Vari ance	Cumul ative %
1	1.42 4	71.1 77	71.177	1.4 24	71.1 77	71.177
2	.576	28.8 23	100.00 0			
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.						

Table 10

Component Matrix^a	
	Component
	1
Completely Un-train any trainee is not possible	.844
Fully Re-train the trainees as desired is another challenge	.844
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.	

Null hypothesis is rejected as the P value is less than 0.05 which means Listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary.

There were 106 statements in the questionnaire. Tests of the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy and Bartlett’s test of sphericity resulted in the correlation matrix presented in above table.

The KMO test for listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary yielded a score of 0.50, which is considered a marvelous degree of common variance (Morgan, 2006).

The Varimax rotation method was chosen to uncover a more meaningful pattern of item factor loadings. Table 9 displays the total variance explained in two stages. At the initial stage, it shows the factors and their associated eigenvalues, percentage of variance explained and the cumulative percentage.

Hypothesis – 3.

H0: Quantifying the ‘transfer of learning’ is not important to ensure training effectiveness.

H1: It is significantly important to find out the challenges faced during quantification of ‘Transfer of Learning’ to ensure training effectiveness.

Table 11

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Minimum	Maximum
Measurement of ‘Transfer of Learning’ of any training is not fully quantifiable	106	4.38	.487	4	5

Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness	106	4.32	.469	4	5
--	-----	------	------	---	---

Table 12

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test				
Ranks				
		N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks
Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness - Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable	Negative Ranks	23 ^a	20.50	471.50
	Positive Ranks	17 ^b	20.50	348.50
	Ties	66 ^c		
	Total	106		
a. Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness < Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable				
b. Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness > Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable				
c. Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness = Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable				

Table 13

Test Statistics^a

	Evaluation and analysis of Summative Feedback for any training is the most essential part to assess Training effectiveness - Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable
Z	-.949 ^b
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.034
a. Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test	
b. Based on positive ranks.	

Wilcoxon Signed Ranks Test revealed (table 13) that, It is significantly ($\text{Sig}=0.034$) important to find out the challenges faced during quantification of 'Transfer of Learning' to ensure training effectiveness Hence, null hypothesis (H_2) is not accepted

4 Findings & Suggestions:

This section discusses descriptive analysis on to identify the reasons for improper Identification of Training Needs and Training Need Analysis.

Proper Identification of Training Needs of employees is a huge task and it is never complete in all respects has a mean value of 4.68 and standard deviation is 0.469.

Measurement of 'Transfer of Learning' of any training is not fully quantifiable has a mean value of 4.38 with standard deviation of 0.487

75% strongly agreed that Scientific Training Needs Analysis is next to impossible, whereas 21% of total populations strongly agreed to completely Un-train any trainee is not possible

4 Conclusion:

It is concluded, that it is significantly important to follow the process of Identification of training needs and carry out "Training Needs Analysis." Also the listing the difficulties encountered in Un-train and Re-train the trainees is significantly necessary. From the hypothesis on training the conclusion is also drawn that it is significantly important to find out the challenges faced during quantification of 'Transfer of Learning' to ensure training effectiveness

References:

1. Rolf P Lyton & Uday Pareek; Training for Organisational Transformation, Sage Publication, New Delhi.
2. A V Petrovsky & M G Yarohevsky; A Concise Psychological Dictionary, Progress Publishers, Moscow.
3. R Thomson; The Psychology of Thinking, Penguin, London, UK
4. Training Material on Direct Trainers' Skill, Thames Valley University, UK.
5. Glossary of Training Terms
6. Robert H Rouda & Mitchell E Kusy Jr.; High Performance Training, in Tappi Journal 1995-96.
7. Carter McNamara, Typical Reasons for Employee Training & Development, www.mapnp.org
8. Roger Cartwright; Training and Development Express – 11.01 Express exec.com, UK.
9. Donald Clark, Introduction to Instructional System Design – 2000, www.nwlink.com.
10. McShane, S.L. & Von Glinow, M.Y. (2013). *Organizational behavior: Emerging Knowledge. Global Reality* (6th ed.). New York, NY: The McGraw-Hill/Irwin.
11. Tulving E. How Many Systems are there? American Psychologist, 1985.
12. Bernstein, Roy, Srull, Wickens. Psychology, Houghton Mifflin Co. Boston.
13. Atkinson, RC & Shiffrin RM. Human Memory: A proposed system and its control processes, 1968. New York.
14. Bernstein, Roy, Srull, Wickens. Psychology, Houghton Mifflin Co. Boston
15. Emily J. Klein, Learning, Unlearning, and Relearning: Lessons from One School's Approach to Creating and Sustaining Learning Communities. Teacher Education Quarterly, Winter 2008.
16. Fiske, S.T. and Taylor, S.E. (1991), *Social Cognition*, 2nd ed., McGraw-Hill, New York, NY.
17. Grisold, T., Kaiser, A. and Hafner, J. (2017), "Unlearning before creating new knowledge: a cognitive process", Proceedings of the 50th HI International Conference on System Sciences, pp. 4610-4623, available at: <http://hdl.handle.net/10125/41723>
18. Nataša R. Learning-forgetting-unlearning, relearning – the learning organization's learning dynamics. Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Croatia. www.emeraldinsight.com/0969-6474.htm
19. Sharma, S. and Lenka, U. (2019), "Exploring linkages between unlearning and relearning in organizations", The Learning Organization, Vol. 26 No. 5.
20. Turc, E. and Baumard, P. (2007), "Can organizations really unlearn?", in McInerney, C.R. and Day, R.E. (Eds), Rethinking Knowledge Management: From Knowledge Objects to Knowledge Processes, Springer, New York, NY, pp. 125-146.
21. Cegarra-Navarro, J.G., Sánchez-Vidal, M.E. and Cegarra-Leiva, D. (2011), "Balancing exploration and exploitation of knowledge through an unlearning context: an empirical investigation in SMEs", Management Decision, Vol. 49 No. 7, pp. 1099-1119

22. Cegarra-Navarro, J.G.C., Wensley, A.K. and Polo, M.T.S. (2014), "A conceptual framework for unlearning in a homecare setting", *Knowledge Management Research and Practice*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 375-386.
23. Zhao, Y., Lu, Y. and Wang, X. (2013), "Organizational unlearning and organizational relearning: a dynamic process of knowledge management", *Journal of Knowledge Management*, Vol. 17 No. 6, pp. 902-912
24. Nataša R. Learning-forgetting-unlearning, relearning – the learning organization's learning dynamics. Faculty of Economics and Business, University of Rijeka, Rijeka, Croatia. www.emeraldinsight.com/0969-6474.htm
25. Vince, R. (2008), "Learning-in-action' and 'learning inaction': advancing the theory and practice of critical action learning", *Action Learning: Research and Practice*, Vol. 5 No. 2, pp. 93-104
26. Huang, D., Chen, S., Zhang, G. and Ye, J. (2018), "Organizational forgetting, absorptive capacity, and innovation performance: a moderated mediation analysis", *Management Decision*, Vol. 56 No. 1, pp. 87-104.
27. Wong, P.S., Whelan, B. and Holdsworth, S. (2018), "Are contractors ready for greater use of prefabrication in projects? An empirical analysis on the role of unlearning and counter knowledge", *International Journal of Construction Management*, pp. 1-16, doi: 10.1080/15623599.2018.1539160
28. Usman, M., Hameed, A.A. and Manzoor, S. (2018), "Exploring the links between ethical leadership and organizational unlearning: a case study of a European multinational company", *Business and Economic Review*, Vol. 10 No. 2, pp. 28-54
29. Nystrom, P.C. and Starbuck, W.H. (1984), "To avoid organizational crises, unlearn", *Organizational Dynamics*, Vol. 12 No. 4, pp. 53-65.
30. Mehrizi, M.H.R. and Lashkarbolouki, M. (2016), "Unlearning troubled business models: from realization to marginalization", *Long Range Planning*, Vol. 49 No. 3, pp. 298-323.
31. Haslinda ABDULLAH, MAJOR CHALLENGES TO THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF HUMAN RESOURCE TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES, *The Journal of International Social Research*, Volume 2 / 8 Summer 2009
32. Becker, G. S. (1975) Human capital: A theoretical and empirical analysis, with special reference to education (2nd ed.). *National Bureau of Economic Research*. New York: Columbia University Press.
33. Schmidt, J. & Lines, S. (2002) A measure of success. *People Management*, 8 (9): pp.32.
34. Harrison, R. and Kessels, J. (2004) *Human Resource Development in a Knowledge Economy: An Organisational View*. New York: Palgrave MacMillan.
35. Nadler, L. and Wiggs, G. D.. (1986) *Managing Human Resource Development. A practical guide*. San Francisco, California, Jossey-Bass Inc.
36. Chalofsky, N. and Reinhart, C. (1988) *Effective human resource development: How to build a strong and responsive HRD function*. San Francisco, California, Jossey-Bass
37. Nadler, L. and Nadler, Z. (1989) *Developing Human Resources*. San Francisco, California, Jossey-Bass.
38. O'Connell, J. (1999) *HR's Next Challenge: Harnessing Individualism*. HR Focus, pp.7-8

**Volume 15 | Special Issue 03 | MARKETING MANAGEMENT-
TOPICAL ISSUES & CHALLENGES**

39. Streumer, J., Van Der Klink, V. and Van De Brink, K. (1999) The future of HRD. *International Journal of Lifelong Education*, 18 (4): pp. 259-274.
40. Harrison, R. (2000) *Employee Development*. (2nd ed) London, Institute of Personnel and Development.
41. Sadler-Smith, E., Down, S., and Lean, J. (2000) "Modern" learning methods: Rhetoric and reality. *Personnel Review*, 29 (4): pp 474-490.
42. Roberts, C. and McDonald, G. (1995) Training to fail. *Journal of Management Development*, 14 (4): pp.16-31.
43. Bing, J. W., Kehrhahn, M. and Short, D. C. (2003) Challenges to the field of human resources development. *Advances in Developing Human Resources*, 5 (3): pp. 342-351.
44. Eidgahy, S. Y. (1995) Management of diverse HRD programs: Challenges and opportunities. *Personnel Management*, 46 (3): pp. 15-20.
45. Garrett J. Endres, Brian H. Klieiner, How To Measure Management Training and Development Effectiveness, *Journal of European Industrial Training*, 2015, MCB UP Ltd.

